

FORMATION OF INSTITUTIONAL CONDITIONS FOR SCIENTIFIC AND INDUSTRIAL INTEGRATION IN THE CONTEXT OF ENSURING ENERGY SECURITY

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Modernizing energy infrastructure, improving energy efficiency, digitalizing energy systems, and developing smart grids are critical to Belarus's energy security. As a small, open economy, Belarus is influenced by global economic trends, including internationalization, economic integration, and technological advancements. The global energy challenge, mainly due to increasing fossil fuel consumption, remains a pressing issue.

The study used standard scientific methods, including observation, description, modeling, and statistical data analysis. The comparative method was used to identify the field and object of monitoring, ensuring comparability of indicators using relative values for evaluation. The dynamics of scientific and industrial integration indicators were analyzed over a nine-year period (2015-2023) using official statistical data from Belarus. Forecasting of indicator values for the next three years (2024-2026) was conducted using linear regression. The main purpose of creating the EAEU energy market is to ensure the energy security of the Member States. This state is achieved by the efficient use of resources (creating conditions for the optimal use of energy resources within the Union) and obtaining a number of economic benefits (promoting the formation of a single energy market, which contributes to increasing competitiveness and stimulating economic growth). Among the main tasks that are set for the period of formation of a common energy market of the EAEU member states are the following: harmonization of the regulatory framework through the development and adoption of common norms and standards for the energy industry; development of general energy infrastructure, including transport networks and energy transmission systems; development of energy trade mechanisms (creation of transparent and efficient mechanisms for energy trade between member countries).

As part of the common energy market development it is necessary to: create a common management body to coordinate and manage the integration process in the energy sector; promote the exchange of experience and the transfer of advanced technologies among member countries; provide financial support for the projects implementation aimed at creating a common energy market; develop mechanisms for the free exchange of energy among member countries, including the development of common rules for trade, the formation of markets and the promotion of competition; develop measures to attract investment in the energy sector to modernize infrastructure, introduce new technologies and improve its efficiency; ensure the diversification of energy sources and the development of renewable energy sources; develop common standards to ensure the compatibility of energy transmission systems and facilitate the integration of national energy systems; carry out regular consultations and agreements between member countries to resolve issues related to energy policy and ensure the coordinated development of the industry.

These proposals can serve as a general guideline, and specific actions may vary according to political, economic and social developments in the region. In the future, the main trends in the

development of the world economy are predicted to be a decrease in the cost of renewable energy facilities.

This article presents an organizational and economic mechanism for achieving the forecast values of the level of the most important indicators of scientific and industrial integration. A systematic approach is considered, including the prerequisites and conditions for the formation of the institutional environment of scientific and industrial integration. The implementation of the scientific and industrial complex development roadmap should be aimed at modernizing infrastructure, increasing the share of high-tech products and creating sustainable ties between all participants.